

“Moves” for Guiding Presentations in French

Nuchanat Handumrongkul, Suwaree Yordchim, Anantachai Aeka

Abstract—Despite four years of study in the tourism industry, the Bachelor’s graduates cannot perform their jobs as experienced tour guides. This research aimed to develop French teaching and studying for Tourism with two main purposes: to analyze ‘Moves’ used in oral presentations at tourist attraction; and to study content in guiding presentations or ‘Guide Speak’. The study employed audio recording of these presentations as an interview method in authentic situations, having four tour guides as respondents and information providers. The data was analyzed via moves and content analysis. The results found that there were eight Moves used; namely, Welcoming, Introducing oneself, Drawing someone’s attention, Giving information, Explaining, Highlighting, Persuading and Saying goodbye. In terms of content, the information being presented covered the outstanding characteristics of the places and well-integrated with other related content. The findings were used as guidelines for curriculum development; in particular, the core content and the presentation forming the basis for students to meet the standard requirements of the labor-market and professional schemes.

Keywords—“Moves”, Guiding Presentation, French.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE tourism industry has played a very important role for Thailand’s economy because it brings in the biggest share of total revenue. Consequently, more jobs are also allocated to people at every level, forming a very strong monetary circulation at the macro economical level. Not only has the employment sector received a positive impact, but also the service sector has gained simultaneously. This is an ideal concept for the new faces in industrial countries where economies are based on providing services. When looking from an in house perspective, tourism can reduce the migration to big cities for work while waiting for the next cultivation season. Furthermore, people in the community can be proud of their own regional artisans, traditions and customs. The continuous promotion by every government since 1949 has illustrated their vision that the tourism industry is the main stream of income, replacing the agricultural sector, and has brought a large amount of earnings to those of in need. The wealth of impressive places and cultures cannot make tourism successful by itself; another important factor is the tour guides, the closest ones to tourists. They are considered as the goodwill ambassador of the country since they have to provide their knowledge and understandings of the socio-economic aspect, culture, tradition, customs and beliefs. Nonetheless, foreign language competence alone cannot be neglected, so a qualified tour guide should possess a good

Nuchanat Handumrongkul, Suwaree Yordchim, and Anantachai Aeka are with the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University (SSRU), Thailand (e-mail: nuchanat.ha@ssru.ac.th, suwaree.yo@ssru.ac.th, anatachai.ae@ssru.ac.th).

personality, interpersonal skills, psychological insight, knowledge and communication skills.

A guiding presentation is a combination of science and art. It is a unique one according to its distinguished style and rhetoric. The major problem being discussed is that the graduates cannot achieve the communicative purposes [1]: giving information; and entertaining the tourists, so a guiding presentation can be recognized as a ‘genre’.

Genre, as described by John Swales, was used to analyze the data because genre is a recognizable communicative classification; and is characterized by a set of communicative purposes identified and mutually recognized by members of professionals or academics [2].

Genre is employed to analyze the frequency of expressions examined in communicative purposes. It is a helpful tool for a certain types of careers where classification is needed to clarify their occurrence, [3] in highly structured usage for communication. A class of genre known as move displays constraints on allowable contributions in terms of their intent, positioning, form and functional value. Swales defined the notion of move as a functional unit in a text used for some identifiable purpose. Therefore, moves are often used to identify the textual regularities in certain genres of communication and to describe the functions of the particular text with integration into the entire job. Regarding communicative purpose of the genre, moves can vary in terms of style and structures. As a result, move analysis is a helpful tool in genre studies since moves are semantic and functional units of texts, which can be identified because of their communicative purposes and linguistic boundaries. To accomplish the objectives of communication in guiding presentation, content analysis ascertains the facts from the key informants, the trends and patterns in texts; meanwhile, it can provide a useful technique to discover and describe the focus of individual, group, institution, or social attention [4]. It also allows inferences to corroborate using other methods of data collection.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. The Corpus: Data Collection

Four registered tour guides, with at least five years’ experience, were chosen using a purposive sampling method. A guiding presentation was defined and framed as the oral presentation for describing or explaining at the tour sites. The content and the language usage, including individual style and technique were recorded systematically, for approximately two-hour periods. During their performance, a must-see tourist attraction in the heart of Bangkok -Wat Pho or the Temple of Reclining Buddha in Bangkok was set as the study field. These records were employed as a corpus.

B. Data Analysis

According to the objectives and goals of this study, curriculum development was primarily focused, with a concentration on the details and a thorough understanding. Information background (facts) and authentic language usage played a very important role. Meanwhile, the analysis procedure was entirely integrated in order to gain productive results. Specifically, those included the criteria for recruiting qualified guides; the setting identification, the presentation recording, the framework analysis, etc. The validity and reliability analysis in terms of moves and content were checked for reliability and consistency.

III. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

A. Results of Moves

Regarding the identification and analysis of 'Moves', the corpus of successful statement was re-analyzed through a clear process until distinct moves were identified and a clear definition for each was developed.

Eight moves were identified in the corpus, namely: Welcoming (W), Introducing oneself (I), Drawing someone's attention (D), Giving information (G), Explaining (E), Highlighting (H), Persuading (P) and Saying goodbye (S).

Move 1: Welcoming. The purpose of this 'Move' is to greet the audience in French or the combination in French and Thai.

Linguistic signals:

- Bonjour. Sawadee Krab/kha.
- Bienvenue à.....

Ex. Bonjour mesdames, messieurs.

Bienvenue à Bangkok. Bienvenue en Thaïlande.

Move 2: Introducing oneself. The purpose of this 'Move' is to suggest the guide's name and his/her duty.

Linguistic signals:

- s'appeler

Ex. Je m'appelle.....

- guide local(e)

Ex. Je suis votre guide locale.

- faire un tour de.....

Ex. Aujourd'hui, nous allons faire un tour du temple ancien.

Move 3: Drawing someone's attention. The purpose of this 'Move' is to let the audience acknowledge where they are, in particular at a famous point, and what they should see or to intentionally link statements / announcements / recognitions or to shift to another topic.

Linguistic signals:

- C'est... / Voilà... / Il y a... / On a.....

Ex. Voilà le Bouddha Couché.

- Je vous emmène voir.....

Ex. Je vous emmène voir Bangkok ancien.

- Maintenant, nous sommes devant /en face de.....

Ex. Maintenant, nous sommes devant le Temple du Bouddha Couché.

- arriver à...

Ex. On arrive au Temple du Bouddha Couché.

Move 4: Giving information. The purpose of this 'Move' is to describe and figure out the historical background and explicit / distinguished characteristics of tourist attraction / point of interests.

Linguistic signals:

- ancien/ vieux

Ex. Wat Pho est un très vieux temple.

- être construit/fondé à l'époque de / au...siècle / en + année

Ex. Ce temple a été construit en 1782.

- faire construire.....

Ex. Le roi Rama I a fait construire ce temple.

Move 5: Explaining. The purpose of this 'Move' is to refer to and clarify tradition, customs, by answering questions 'why' and 'how' including the similarities or differences.

Linguistic signals:

- Dans notre tradition,.....

Ex. Dans notre tradition, même si un temple est très vieux, on ne peut pas le détruire.

- comme / être considéré comme

Ex. Les bonzes sont considérés comme des enseignants.

- ressembler à.....

Ex. L'acupuncture chinoise, les techniques des aiguilles des Chinois ont accéléré la ligne du corps pour pouvoir la puissance et l'électricité dans notre corps peut guérir notre maladie. Mais le diagramme anatomie dans le wat Pho, ce sont les copies originales de techniques d'accélérer notre puissance de corps par les doigts, par les points du corps du masseur. Ça, c'est le technique acupressure. Ça ressemble à l'acupuncture.

- être différent de

Ex. L'acupuncture est différent de l'acupressure.

- c'est-à-dire...

Ex. Le Bouddha Couché, cela veut dire que le Bouddha qui est en train d'atteindre au nirvana.

Move 6: Highlighting. The purpose of this 'Move' is to concentrate on exotic values of objects / decorations / construction / environment or locations for the pleasure and satisfaction of the visitors.

Linguistic signals:

- adjectives d'appréciation: magnifique, splendide, important
- le / la plus + adjectivedu pays / du monde

Ex. Wat Pho est un temple splendide. Ce temple est le temple le plus vieux de Bangkok.

Move 7: Persuading. The purpose of this 'Move' is to invite the audience to do something or to come back to that location again.

Linguistic signals:

- Allez voir.....

Ex. Allez voir la statue principale à l'intérieure du temple.

- N'oubliez pas de....

Ex. N'oubliez pas de penser à faire le massage n'importe où avant de quitter la Thaïlande.

Move 8: Saying goodbye. The purpose of this 'Move' is to invite or request the audiences to participate in any activities or to insist the visitors to be on track.

Linguistic signals:

- la fin de la promenade

Ex. Alors maintenant, on s'approche petit à petit l'endroit de la fin de la promenade.

- vous avous amusez
- plaire à

Ex. J'espère que cette visite vous a plu.

- pouvoir vous rendre service à nouveau

Ex. Peut-être un jour si vous retournez, nous espérons pouvoir vous rendre service à nouveau.

- Merci beaucoup / Je vous remercie de
- Au revoir
- Bonne journée / Bonne soirée / Bon séjour

Ex. Merci beaucoup mesdames et messieurs. Au revoir.

Fig. 1 The cycle of guiding presentation

According to Fig. 1, the flow of guiding presentations begins with Move "W" Welcoming and then to Move "I" Introducing oneself, the guide introduces himself and his duty. After that, it is Move "D" or Drawing the audience's attention, followed by Move "G" Giving information. Next is Move "G", moving into a loop among Move "E" Explaining, Move "H" Highlighting and Move "P" Persuading where information is given, elaborated, focused and given according to the importance or distinguished point of interest. The presentations end up with Move "S" saying goodbye including their hopes of satisfaction and gratitude.

B. Results of Content Analysis

TABLE I
CONTENT ANALYSIS, PRINCIPAL DESCRIPTION TOPICS

Topics	G1	G2	G3	G4
1. Background of the Temple Overall				
- Period of construction	✓	✓	✓	✓
- The Founder and Royal Patronage	✓	-	✓	✓
- Recognition as the first university of Thailand	✓	✓	✓	✓
- Signification of the Original Name	-	✓	✓	-
2. The Reclining Buddha				
- Background	-	✓	✓	✓
- Postures and Significance	-	✓	✓	✓
- Dimension	✓	✓	✓	✓
- Material & Elements	✓	✓	✓	✓
- Other Important Features: Image Features, 108 auspicious Symbols, Mother of Pearl Decorations	✓	✓	✓	✓
3. Thai Traditional Massage: Anatomy on the wall, Comparison with Chinese Acupuncture	✓	✓	✓	✓
4. The Main Chapel				
- The Principal Buddha Statue	✓	✓	-	✓
- Chronological Construction	✓	-	-	✓
- The Ashes of King Rama I	✓	-	-	✓
5. The Four Great Chedis	✓	-	-	-
6. The Cloister	✓	-	-	✓
7. Others				
- Hermits' Postures	✓	-	-	-
- 32 Significant Characteristic of the Great Man	-	-	✓	-
- Ways to make merit	-	-	✓	-

REFERENCES

- [1] Kriengsak Chareonwong. *ASEAN Economic Community and Globalization: Ways of Thai Tour Guide Adaptation*. Retrieved May 21, 2013, from www. Bangkokbiznews.com.
- [2] John Swales. *Genre analysis: English in academic and research settings*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1990.
- [3] Brian A. Rutherford. *Genre Analysis of Corporate Annual Report Narrative. A Corpus Linguistics-Based Approach*. Kent: University of Kent.
- [4] RP Weber. *Basic Content Analysis*. SAGE University, 1990.
- [5] Surachart Suansap. *English for Tourism V : The Guide Speak*. Bangkok: Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, 2002.
- [6] Rian Lowimongkol. *French Tourist Behavior*. Journal of the University of Thai Chamber of Commerce. 2004.

From the table above, the historical background of the temple, the characteristic of the place recognized as the first university of Thailand, the grandeur and exotic appearance of the Reclining Buddha were thoroughly presented. Noticeably, background, posture, dimension, materials & elements and other characteristics in terms of decoration and depiction of Thai traditional massage in comparison to Chinese acupuncture were also remarked upon. In addition, the principal Buddha statue itself was attracted and worth attention. Moreover, all mentioned were integrated in the guides' presentations along with other Buddhism's perception, including ways of merit making, 32 significant signs of great men, etc.

IV. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This study examined and described the features of moves found in guiding presentation. Eight functional moves were identified: Welcoming, Introducing oneself, Drawing someone's attention, Giving information, Explaining, Highlighting, Persuading and Saying goodbye. The findings were in line with Surachart Suansap's [5]. The procedures being presented by most guides always began with greetings and introducing oneself, followed by highlighting and describing geographical location, historical background and other outstanding features, respectively. It ended up with closing the tour by expressing thanks and saying goodbye. However, what the research has found were additional details in giving information with explanation, highlighting and persuading that is interwoven before closing the tour or saying goodbye. Concerning the content, the tour guides should possess knowledge of history, Thai culture, botanical science, Thai traditional medicine and other anecdotes. Similarly, Rian Lowimongkol [6] commented that French tourists always brought a pocket book about Thailand, having bunches of details about tourist attractions, Thai traditions, ways of Thai life and history. Certainly, they expect additional knowledge, content and a better understanding beyond the pocket book they have read; like the Chinese stone statues, demons, Thai rituals - ordination ceremony, monk's way of life, etc.

For future aspect, the result of this research could be adaptable and applied for curriculum development; in particular, in the core content for French and other languages for Tourism. Lecturers should concentrate on various moves in order to form patterns and process of communication with the content, consisting of general background and other outstanding characteristics by integrating knowledge about Thailand in an interesting and innovative way. Authentically, the students, who would gain the utmost benefit, could possess the qualifications required by the labor-market, and could respond to the indicators for academic content standards for a professional tour guide.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Very special thanks to Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University for funding this project and Assoc. Prof. Dr. Luedech Girdwichai, whose services were invaluable to this study.